

EFFECT OF BROODFISH SEX ON GROWTH PERFORMANCE OF NILE TILAPIA (*Oreochromis niloticus*) REARED IN HAPAS

Falaye Augustine Eyiwunmi¹, Omoike Augustine^{2*} Obibi Omotitiri Sandra¹

1. Department of Aquaculture and Fisheries Management, University of Ibadan, Ibadan, Nigeria

2. Department of Biological Sciences, Bells University of Technology, P.M.B. 1015, Ota, Nigeria

ABSTRACT

The study was carried out to investigate the effect of brood fish sex on growth performance of Nile tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) reared in hapas for the period of 14 weeks. Brood fish sex ratios (Male: Female) used in this experiment were 1:2, 3:1, 2:2 and 1:3. Treatments were replicated thrice. The fish were fed twice daily at 3% body weight. Relevant growth performance parameters were determined. Also, water quality parameters were monitored. The data obtained were subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA). It was observed that the average weight gain (AWG) of treatment MF₁ (85.96±7.21 g) and MF₃ (84.1±5.17 g) were significantly different from MF₂ (81.07±4.02 g) and MF₄ (81.36±4.94 g). The body weight gain (BWG), percentage body weight gain (PBWG) and specific growth rate was highest in MF₁ and was significantly different from other treatments. Also, the average daily weight gain of MF₁ (0.19±0.04 g) and MF₃ (0.18±0.32 g) were significantly different from MF₂ (0.13±0.07 g) and MF₄ (0.12±0.31 g).

KEYWORDS: Brood fish, Sex ratio, Growth performance, Nile tilapia and Hapa

Received for Publication: 22/12/13

Accepted for Publication: 10/09/14

Corresponding Author: dromoike@yahoo.com

INTRODUCTION

Nile tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) has been identified as one of the most cultured fish species in the world and is one of the most popular species of the bony fish (Abdel, Mousa, Hand, Ahmed, and Salar 2007; Offem, Akegbejo and Omoniyi 2007) but its culture is still at infancy in African especially Nigeria. This is largely due to poor understanding of its culture technology as relates to growth performance of brood fish among other factors. *O. niloticus* is linked to many positive qualities which include tolerance to poor water quality, wide range of food, plasticity in growth, firm flesh and good taste (Ugwumba, 1988) and the ability to efficiently convert organic and domestic waste into high quality protein (de Graaf, Gelemoni, and Huisman, 1999). The growth of tilapia depends on several factors and it is important to take these factors into consideration. These factors may include the water quality, temperature, oxygen levels, stocking density and the general health of the fish. The type of food provided to the fish and in what quantities will naturally be of imperative importance to the growth. Brood-fish productivity clearly represents the most significant constraints on commercial tilapia production. Increased knowledge of the factors regulating brood-fish productivity is of great importance to the further development of tilapia culture (Coward and Bromage, 2000). Thus, the improvements in our understanding on the appropriate culture conditions and management procedure for brood-fish will be very essential; hence the aim of this study was to determine the growth performance of *O. niloticus* brood-fish under different sex ratio.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Experimental Fish and Acclimation: Brood-fish of *Oreochromis niloticus* were collected from the Department of Aquaculture and Fisheries Management Research Farm. Fish varying in size with an average weight of 74g were selected. Twenty one Males and twenty four Females brood-fish of *O. niloticus* were used for the

All rights reserved

This work by [Wilolud Journals](http://www.wiloludjournals.com) is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 Unported License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/3.0/).

experiment. The fish were kept in conditioning hapas for acclimation for two weeks to adapt to the new environment.

Culture Medium: Nets with a mesh size of 1.5mm and surface area dimension of 0.95×0.50m with stocking ratio of four fish (male and female) per hapa was used. Hapas were suspended and placed in an experimental earthen pond to maintain a water depth of 0.6m inside the hapa. The hapas served as the culture medium for the experiment. The mixed sex of tilapia were kept in the hapas at sex ratios of 1:2 (control), 3:1, 2:2, and 1:3 male to female representing different experimental treatments of MF₁, MF₂, MF₃ and MF₄. Each treatment was replicated thrice. Hapas were tied to a stake with a rope. Sinkers were tied at the bottom edges of each hapas to allow stability in water. Water was pumped into the pond regularly to maintain the desired level of 0.6m in the hapas.

Feeding Procedure: The Brood fish were fed twice daily with a commercial pelleted diet at 3% body weight, 0900hrs and 1700hrs. The fish pellets were sourced from Vital feed® and contained 30% crude protein.

Experimental Fish Sampling: Weights of the fish were measured fortnightly using the AND sensitive weighing scale of SK-1000 measuring to the nearest 0.5g.

Growth Performance Parameters for Experimental Fish: The Growth Performance Parameters were calculated according to Olevera-Novea *et al.* (1990) using the following equation:

Average Weight Gain (AWG): This was determined by calculating the difference between the initial weight and the final weight of the fish.

$$AWG = W_2 - W_1$$

Where W_1 = initial weight
 W_2 = final weight.

Average Daily Weight Gain (ADWG) :This was determined by calculating the difference between the initial weight and the final weight divided by time.

$$ADWG = \frac{W_2 - W_1}{t(days)}$$

Percentage Weight Gain (PWG) :This will be determined from the relationship between the total weights gains of the fish expressed as a percentage of the initial weight.

$$PWG = \frac{final\ weight}{initial\ weight} \times 100$$

Specific Growth Rate (SGR) :This will be determined from the relationship of the differences in weight of the fish within the experimental period.

$$SGR = \frac{100[LnWt1 - LnWt0]}{t}$$

Where Ln= natural logarithm
 Wt_0 = initial weight (g)
 Wt_1 =final weight (g)
 t = time of day

All rights reserved

This work by [Wilolud Journals](#) is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 Unported License](#).

Water Quality Parameters: Temperature, pH and dissolved oxygen (DO) were monitored during the period of the experiment. Temperature of the water were taken twice a day (8pm and 4pm) using the mercury in glass thermometer calibrated in degree Celsius. Dissolved oxygen was measured using the titration method. pH was measured with a digital pH meter (model checker I produced by Hanna Instrument Company). The pH and Dissolved Oxygen were measured weekly.

Statistical Analysis :Data collected fromthis experiment were subjected to one way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) using the SARS for window evaluation version. Means of treatments were separated by Duncan (1955) Multiple Range Test (DMRT).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results

Table 1 indicates the growth performance parameters of *O. niloticus* brood-fish sex ratio. From the result obtained from this study as shown in table 4.1, the variation in the mean average initial body weight among the treatments did not show any significant difference. The mean final body weight of MF₁ (85.96±7.21 g) and MF₃ (84.10±5.17 g) were significantly different ($P < 0.05$) from MF₂ (81.07±4.02 g) and MF₄ (81.36±4.94 g).

The body weight gain, percentage body weight gain and specific growth rate was highest in MF₁, it is closely followed by that of the fish in treatment MF₃. Fish kept in treatment MF₂ and MF₄ had the least body weight gain, percentage body weight gain and specific growth rate.

The performance for the average daily weight gain obtain from this study indicates that treatment MF₁and MF₃ with mean values of 0.19±0.04g and 0.18±0.32g were significantly different ($P < 0.05$) from treatment MF₂and MF₄ with mean values of 0.13±0.07g and 0.12±0.31g respectively.

Figure 1 shows the trend for growth performance parameters of *O. niloticus* brood-fish sex ratio of initial body weight final body weight, body weight gain, percentage body weight gain, specific growth rate and the average daily weight gain.

Figure 2 shows the trend of bi-weekly mean weight gain for *O. niloticus* under different sex ratio for fourteen weeks. It was observed that treatment MF₁ showed highest growth performance from the 8th week and was followed by MF₃ which was closely followed by MF₄. The least performance was observed in treatment MF₂

Table 1: Growth Performance Parameters of *Oreochromis niloticus* Brood-fish Sex Ratio (Mean ± SD)

Parameters	MF ₁	MF ₂	MF ₃	MF ₄
Initial Body Weight	74.23 ± 0.21 ^a	74.10 ± 0.20 ^a	74.27 ± 0.15 ^a	73.97 ± 0.76 ^a
Gain (g)				
Final Body Weight	85.96 ± 7.21 ^a	81.07 ± 4.02 ^b	84.10 ± 5.17 ^a	81.36 ± 4.94 ^b
Gain (g)				
Body Weight Gain	11.73 ± 7.20 ^a	6.97 ± 3.96 ^c	9.83 ± 5.17 ^b	7.39 ± 4.94 ^c
(g)				
% Body Weight	15.79 ± 9.69 ^a	9.39 ± 5.33 ^c	13.19 ± 6.94 ^b	9.93 ± 6.69 ^c
Gain				
Specific Growth	0.24 ± 0.05 ^a	0.16 ± 0.37 ^c	0.23 ± 0.04 ^b	0.16 ± 0.03 ^c
Rate				
Average Daily	0.19 ± 0.04 ^a	0.13 ± 0.07 ^b	0.18 ± 0.32 ^a	0.12 ± 0.31 ^b
Weight Gain (g)				

Means in the same column having the same superscript are not significantly different from each other by DMRT ($P < 0.05$) as determined by ANOVA

All rights reserved

This work by [Wilolud Journals](#) is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 Unported License](#).

Fig 1: Growth performance parameters of *Oreochromis niloticus* brood-fish sex ratio

Fig 2: Bi-weekly mean weight gain of *Oreochromis niloticus* under different sex ratio for fourteen weeks.

Table 2 shows the mean value for water quality parameters. The water quality parameters monitored during the experimental period include temperature, dissolved oxygen (DO) and pH.

From the results obtained in table 4.4, it indicates that mean temperature value was within the range of 27.48 ± 0.11 - 32.23 ± 0.09 throughout the period of the experiment. Mean dissolved oxygen measured was within the range of 3.25 ± 0.15 - 4.45 ± 0.05 and mean pH level measured was within the range of 7.5 ± 0.25 - 8.5 ± 0.18 throughout the period of the experiment.

Table 2: Mean Values for Weekly Water Parameters

Parameters	Value
Temperature (°C)	27.48 ± 0.11 - 32.23 ± 0.09
Dissolved Oxygen	3.25 ± 0.15 - 4.45 ± 0.05
pH	7.5 ± 0.25 - 8.5 ± 0.18

All rights reserved

This work by [Wilolud Journals](http://www.wiloludjournals.com) is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 Unported License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/3.0/).

Discussion

This present study was aimed at describing the effect of brood-fish sex ratio on growth performance of Nile tilapia. The growth performance of brood-stock sex ratio of Blue tilapia reared in hapas has been observed by Khalfalla, Hammouda, Tahoun, and Abo-State (2008). The use of brood-fish sex ratio will provide a practical means of improving growth performance of brood-fish. This present study has shown that, the sex ratio of 1:2 which had the highest performance will improve the growth performance of *O. niloticus*.

The lower growth performance which was observed in higher male to female (3:1) sex ratio would be due to conditions such as competition for space, food and the opposite sex. Rakocy and McGinty (1989) stated that the percentage of females mistakenly included in a population of mostly male tilapia affects the maximum attainable size of the original stock in grow-out ponds.

The main reason tilapia makes a relatively small contribution in most countries, in spite of their desirable traits, is their early sexual maturity. Tilapias reproduce when they are only a few months old, often below market price. Fryer and Iles (1972) points out that lakes in African, it is usually common in the cichlid populations that males generally exhibit more growth than the females. This would be as a result that females reach their sexual maturity before the males.

The early sexual maturity in tilapia may have a negative influence on growth rate (Morales, 1991). A reduction in somatic growth can lead to stunted growth of *O. niloticus* which is often seen as a major problem in tilapia farming. Consequently, the growth rate of adult tilapia decreases though, fewer marketable sized fish are harvested (de Graaf *et al.*, 1999).

The growth of *O. niloticus* will depend on several factors such as water quality (temperature, dissolved oxygen etc) stocking density and the general health of the fish. When water quality parameters are not measured properly, this may lead to poor growth or death of fish.

The nutrition and feeding regime will depend on the success of growth performance of tilapia fish (Chong *et al.*, 2004). Growth is usually retarded when high feeding levels per unit area required to support high sex ratios produces poor water quality. When feeding a nutritionally incomplete diet, growth may be further slowed. Feed is usually important in the growth performance of fish. Tilapia fish fed a nutritionally complete diet would not need natural foods for rapid growth. Also when fed at a higher feeding rates water quality becomes deteriorated and this will often cause constraints to fish growth.

Fish farmers will need to apply the correct and appropriate sex ratios improved feed quality and monitored the environmental conditions so as to maintain a faster growth of brood-fish.

CONCLUSION

The growth performance of *O. niloticus* was affected by the sex ratio of males to female. It is further observed that, stocking a larger number of male and fewer female will greatly have adverse effect on their growth performance. Sex ratio of closely or equal proportion would be ideal for stocking. However, literatures had it that male tilapia grows faster than the female; though there are conditions which will also retard the growth of females.

Oreochromis niloticus when given adequate nutrition will perform well in growth. Fish generally will not only depend on nutrition, however, a suitable environment such as temperature, dissolve oxygen (DO) and pH. Water parameters not properly measured will probably have adverse effect on growth or lead to death of fish.

REFERENCES

Abdel, T.M., Mousa, A.A., Hand, M., Ahmed, A. and Salar, S.F.M. (2007). The Use of Calcium Pre-exposure as a Protective Agent against Environmental Copper Toxicity for Juvenile Nile Tilapia, *Oreochromis niloticus* (Linnaeus 1958). *Aquaculture*, 264: 236-246

All rights reserved

This work by [Wilolud Journals](#) is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 Unported License](#).

- Adesulu, E.A., (2001). *Pisciculture in Nigeria: Essential Production Information*. Eternal Communication Limited. 14 Oluruntedo Street, Majiyagbe, Ipaja, Lagos.120p
- Chong , A.S.C., Ishale. S.D., Osman Z. and Hashim R. (2004).Effect of Dietary Protein Level on the Reproductive Performance of Female Swordtails *Xiphophorus helleri* (Poeciliidae).*Aquaculture*, 234: 381-392
- Clucas, I.J. (1981). Fish Handling, Preservation and Processing in the tropics. Part 1 Edited by Clucas I.J. Tropical Development and Research Institute, London
- Coward, K. and Bromage, N.R., (2000). Reproductive Physiology of Female tilapia Brood-stock.*Reviews in Fish Biology and Fisheries*, 10:1-25
- De Graaf, G.J., Gelemoni, F. and Huisman, E.A. (1999). Reproductive Biology of Pond Reared Nile Tilapia, *Oreochromis niloticus* (Linn). *Aqua. Resource*, 30:25-33
- Duncan, D.B., (1985). Multiple Ranges and Multiple F-test .*Biometrics*, 11:1-42
- Fryer, G. and Iles, T.D. (1972). The cichlid Fishes of the Great Lakes of African: Their Biological and Evolution. Oliver and Boyd, Edinburgh, Scotland, Pp.641
- Hammouda, Y.A.F., Ibrahim, M.A.R., Zale El-Din, M.M.A., Eid, A.M.S., Magouz, F.I. and Tahoun A.M. (2008). Effect of Dietary Protein Levels and Sources on Reproductive Performance and Seed Quality of Nile Tilapia *Oreochromis niloticus*(Linn) Brood-stock. *Abbassa International Journal*,1 A:55-78
- Khalfalla, M.M., Hammouda, Y.A., Tahoun, A.M. and Abo-State, H.A.M. (2008).Effect of Brood-stock Sex Ratio on Growth and Reproductive Performance of Blue Tilapia, *Oreochromis aureus*(Steindachner) reared in hapas. Proceedings of the 8th International Symposium on Tilapia in Aquaculture, October 12-14, 2008, the Central Laboratory for Aquaculture Research, Cairo, Egypt, pp: 115-125
- Morales, D.A. (1991). La Tilapia en México. Biología, Cultivo y Pesquerías. AG, México,D.F. 190 page
- Offem, B.O., Akegbejo, Y.S., and Omoniyi, I.J. (2007).Biological Assessment of *Oreochromis niloticus* (Pisces: Cichlidae; Linn, 1958) in a Tropical Flood Plain river.*African Jour. Biotech.*, 6: 1966-1971
- Olevera-Novea, M.E., Couprous G.S., Sabido G.M. and Martinez Pela Cious, C.A. (1990). The Use of Alfafa Leaf Protein concentrates as a Protein Source in Diet of Tilapia (*Oreochromis mosambicus*) *Aquaculture* 83: 45-58
- Omotosho, J.S., Fagade, S.O. and Adebisi, A.A.(1990). Studies on Some Aspects of the Reproductive Biology of Two Cichlids, *Tilapia Zilli* (Gervias) and *S. niloticus* (Linnaeus: Trewavas) from Oba Reservoir, Ibadan, Nigeria. *Niger. J. Natur. Res.*, 59:27-32
- Rakocy, J.E. and McGinty, A.S. (1989).Pond Culture of Tilapia. Southern Regional Aquaculture Centre (SRAC). Publication No. 280. 4p
- Ugwumba, O.A. (1998). Food and Feeding Habits of Juveniles of Some Cultured Species in Nigeria NIOMR Technical Paper, 31:1-20

All rights reserved

This work by [Wilulud Journals](#) is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 Unported License](#).